

Pragmatics of Non-Professional Translation: The Case of Turkish TV Series

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Abstract: Nowadays, information and the speed of its delivery to recipients determine success in many spheres, including entertainment, and audio-visual translation plays a vital role in reaching a broad audience, particularly with popular TV shows, series, and soap operas/TV Series. However, overnight translation of audio-visual content usually results in several inaccuracies, especially at the level of pragmatics. The article discusses the issues of TV Series' non-professional/amateur translation from Turkish into Russian. In most cases, the issues are caused by computer-assisted translation and lack of editing since the high speed of translation is prioritized over its quality. Russian voiceovers and subtitles of popular Turkish TV series "The Oath" ("Yemin"), "Mrs. Fazilet and Her Daughters" ("Fazilet Hanım ve Kızları"), and "The Golden Boy" ("Yalı Çapkını"), translated by different groups of amateurs. Such TV series are used as research material for comparative analysis of incorrect translation of pragmatics. The excerpts with the cases of incorrect pragmatics' rendering are determined using a continuous sampling technique from 22570 minutes of the TV Series. The authors attempt to classify the most common issues of commercialized non-professional translation affecting perceptions of the target audience by inaccuracies in portraying characters, mismatching semantic and pragmatic components of corresponding lexis in source and target languages, and using inconsistent cultural connotations and inappropriate idioms with emotive coloring different in source and target languages.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Çeviri
Edimbilim
TV dizisi
Seslendirme
Amatör çeviri

Amatör Çevirilere Edimbilimsel Bir Bakış: Türk TV Dizileri Örneği

Özet: Günümüzde bilginin alıcılara ulaşma hızı, eğlence sektörü de dahil olmak üzere pek çok alanda başarıyı belirlemektedir. Görsel-ışitsel çeviri, özellikle popüler TV programları ve TV dizileri ile geniş kitlelere ulaşmada önemli bir rol oynayan böylesi bir akış, görsel-ışitsel içeriğin çabucak çevrilmesi, özellikle edimbilimsel düzeyde ciddi metinsel ve iletişimsel hatalara sebebiyet vermektedir. Bu makalede dizilerin profesyonel olmayan, amatör çeviriciler tarafından Türk dilinden Rus diline çevrilmesi sorunu ele alınmaktadır. Genelde böylesi çevirilerde beliren sorunların asıl nedeni çevirilerin bilgisayar destekli yapılması ve gereken düzeltme ve düzenlemelere zaman ayrılmamasıdır çünkü yüksek çeviri hızının kalitesini ve doğruluğunu düşürmektedir. Popüler Türk dizisi "Yemin" ve DiziMania, TURK STAR, Turkish Pembe Dizi ve Türk Dizi gibi farklı amatör gruplar tarafından internet üzerinden çevrilen "Fazilet Hanım ve Kızları" ve "Yalı Çapkını" gibi çeviriler bu çalışmanın ele aldığı metinleri oluşturmaktadır. Çalışmada, önce, dizilerdeki edimbilimsel hatalar taşıyan kısımlar 22,570 dakikalık ham veriden sürekli örnekleme tekniği kullanılarak ayrılmıştır. Yazarlar, karakterleri tasvir etmede karşılaşılan hatalar, kaynak ve hedef dillerde birbirlerine karşılık gelen sözcüklerin karşılaştırılmasında anlam ve edimbilimsel bileşenlerin uyumsuzluğunu ortaya koymuştur.

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1. Introduction

The modern era is commonly described as a period of high-speed and intense sharing of a bulk of compressed information. One of the most highly valued parameters is the speed of information delivery from a sender to a recipient. Media (both conventional and online) plays a critical role in the dissemination of information. Despite the growing influence of the internet, television remains a significant medium for cultural production and dissemination, continuing to play an essential role in contemporary mass communication (Fiske & Hartley, 2003; Postman, 2006; Zorba, 2019). In line with this, media (conventional media or digital media) products still incorporate cultural and linguistic aspects that portray, at least to some extent, the social realities of a given society (Arikan, 2016).

Translation made almost “day to day” is partly based on the automatic processing of text information to be subsequently corrected. Rodríguez Fernández-Peña (2023) states that

The audio-visual translation landscape has radically changed in the lapse of two decades thanks to the arrival of cutting-edge technology and the availability and affordability of fast Internet connections, which has resulted in translation entrepreneurs setting up their own businesses as freelancers or SMEs. With the arrival of the new millennium, the AVT industry saw the advent of online voice talents as new professionals within the revoicing sector (mainly voiceover and dubbing). This sector has grown exponentially ever since (p. 29).

Heaney (2011) posits that two major theoretical forces shape our understanding of the function of translation in today’s world:

Zhong (2006, p. 159) sees translation as one of the liberal arts and views translation training from a humanistic standpoint. Schopp (2006), on the other hand, approaches the issue of correction and assessment from an avowedly vocational viewpoint, a didactic context in which anticipating clients’ needs and striving for customer satisfaction are the ultimate aims (p. 233).

This bifurcation in how we should perceive the function of translation the absolute speed of data transfer has also affected the entertainment industry, including TV series, as the phenomenological interest in TV series found easily on the web has made their appearance an attractive pass-time activity for mass audiences. However, linguistic problems associated with the translation of TV series are also of some interest and determine the relevance of this study since they are examples of the issues related to the processing of information during translation, especially such translation where the focus is on the speed rather than quality of information rendering. Hence, translators often make such translations for “fans” of a particular culture (in our case, it is Turkish culture). With all these in mind, the present study discusses the pragmatic value of translating TV series from Turkish to Russian by non-professional/amateur translators.

2. Literature Review

“While subtitling and dubbing have been attracting interest in both research and teaching at the university level, other techniques such as voiceover have been left aside or not clearly understood” (Orero, 2009, p. 130). Pragmatic aspects of translation, especially in the frame of voice and for such languages as Turkish and Russian, seem to be “terra nova” in translation studies. Traditionally, pragmatic aspects of translation were defined, first of all, as applying to the addressee, who is the recipient of the translation; so it requires taking into account the effect produced by both the original text and its translation (Nelyubin, 2008,

p.163). Schweitzer (1971) argues that the source and the target texts are usually addressed to different recipients. In particular, various researchers suggest a pragmatic criterion for evaluating the adequacy and accuracy of translations (Schweitzer, 1970, p. 31).

Schweitzer (1971) also maintains that the outcome of each translation depends both on the relationships between the text of a source language and the text of the target language and also on the relationships between the translator and other participants in the communication (which is not and may not be considered by machine translation but constantly done by a translator when rendering any text, in some cases relying on intuition). Even when there is no direct contact between the translator and other participants in the communication, the translator perceives the source text as a message from a specific sender addressing a specific recipient. Hence, formulating messages in the target language necessitates considering the audience to whom the translation is addressed (Garbovsky, 2016).

Thus, it is necessary to single out from the relevant texts in the target language some discursive structures that could be used in translation with similar semantics and pragmatism. According to Chaume (2002), considering these in audio-visual translation creates opportunities for developing creativity, gives an idea of the boundaries of the translator's freedom, and demonstrates, from a methodological point of view, exceptional transparency regarding understanding the functions of audio-visual translation. Needless to say, "a pragmatics-based approach to translation would have translators discover all they can about the discourse and utterance contexts of the source-language interaction" (Helmreich & Farwell, 1998, p. 34).

3. Materials and Methods

We focus on something other than professional dubbing since it requires much time and various technical resources. The novelty of this study is due, firstly, to the selection of factual material and, secondly, to analyzing the possible adverse effect of incorrect audio-visual translation on the recipient. This study is based on the translation of three Turkish TV series. The authors have selected the problems of rendering pragmatic information based on continuous sampling during the series viewing. The authors of the present paper analyzed 7000 minutes of speech extracted from "Mrs Fazilet and her Daughters," 8850 minutes from the first two series of "The Oath," and 6720 minutes from "The Golden Boy," all of which were previously translated by amateurs.¹ Our research focused instead on mistranslation (Dharmawan et al., 2019) cases presupposed by using AI or computer-assisted translation tools by a team of non-professional translators (Mabungela, 2023). Hence, individual feelings and moods are not so crucial for our research.

4. Results and Discussion

We have identified several problems that arise from non-professional, commercial translations of Turkish TV series. Our results show that pragmatic inaccuracies lead to complete character distortion, as we have identified 38 cases of incorrect character attributes. For 22,570 minutes of viewing three 3 TV series, in total, we identified 394 repeated cases of translation for the Turkish *besleme* as Russian *soderzhanika* (*кодержанка*) (*kept mistress*), which indicates a reasonably high frequency and typical error made by different translation teams. Besides, even at the level of dictionary definitions, this translation option is not perceived as an exact analogue, cf.: *besleme* 1. *servant (working for subsistence)* 2. *those who live at the expense of*

¹ These series were viewed from www.kinopoisk.ru

someone's help [demek]. They chose direct meaning - *the person who is given money*. However, the fact is that the pragmatic meaning, which has already been reflected in Russian lexicographical sources, completely contradicts the characteristics of the series' characters. The Russian voiceover about the main character in "The Oath" says:

*Damned **kept mistress!** She ruined everything! She will destroy my son!*
*Проклятая **содержанка!** Она все испортила! Она погубит моего сына!*
*Allah'm cezası **besleme.** Her şey mahvetti. Oğlumun başını yakacak.*

This lexical unit completely contradicts the character because, firstly, it refers to a married young woman; secondly, according to the scriptwriters, honor and dignity are in the foreground for the main character Reyhan. Thirdly, the next aspect, as important as the others, is the case of Reyhan, a religious Muslim woman, which fundamentally contradicts the behaviour denoted by the word *kept mistress*:

*I don't know how it happened, but this little **kept mistress** found where Zeynep is.*
*Я не знаю, как это произошло, но эта маленькая **содержанка** нашла, где Зейнеп.*
*Nasıl oldu bilmiyorum, ama o küçük **besleme** Zeynep'in yerini bulmuş.*
*Damned **kept mistress** are the only problem.*
*Гадина, мерзкая **содержанка**, все это из-за тебя.*
*Pislik, pis **besleme.** Her senin yüzünden.*

Interestingly, the same word is also applied to the off-screen character, Reyhan's mother: "She is a daughter of that *kept mistress* Meryem." However, Meryem, whom the viewers see only in the photograph, is a relative of the main character, Hikmet, who is the father of the household, necessitating respectful addressing. Secondly, the viewers see a photograph of a woman in a headscarf, a Muslim, strictly observing the traditions of Islam, and learn about her righteous lifestyle from other characters. Thus, the negative content and pragmatic component of "leading a dubious lifestyle" are entirely inconsistent with how the character is depicted through the translated material. Hence, linguistic and non-linguistic systems of the film text, which operates signs of various kinds, come into conflict (Gumovskaya & Poltorakova, 2023):

Symbol signs serve the linguistic system; the non-linguistic system is by index signs and icon signs. ... the non-linguistic system includes video sequences-iconic and/or indexical signs (people, animals, fantastic creatures, objects) that carry out a sequence (chain) of movements. The video sequence represents the internal structure of the movie; moreover, it characterizes the movie as a whole, as a unity of sound and image. [(Slyshkin & Yefremova, 2004, p. 22).

The third character with the aforementioned negative characteristics is also associated with 11-12-year-old girl Zeynep. She was an orphan accommodated by a wealthy family. The logic of translation based on direct semantic correspondences is obvious: *beslemek* - to give money, *besleme* - a person who is given money, therefore the *kept mistress*. The situation is complicated by the fact that in modern Russian, there are pretty precise semantic correspondences. However, they are in the passive rather than in the active vocabulary of a native speaker of modern Russian: *Prizhivalka* (toadeater - *приживалка*), *nakhlebnitsa* (scrounge - *нахлебница*). The last word is used in translation, but, unfortunately, only twice; in our opinion, it is the most appropriate and the closest equivalent to *besleme*. Such misinterpretation indicates low contextualization of the audio-visual amateur translation. Based on the Russian National Corpus data, it becomes possible to assert that all three of the above analogues are currently not widely used (in the last few years, the frequency of use of all three words tends to zero);

however, the Russian National Corpus provides 77 texts, 97 examples (Fig. 1) for word *soderzhasnka* (*kept mistress – содержанка*), and it is a more significant number of texts with word *kept mistress* causes the translation program to use such word. The Russian National Corpus presents eight texts, eight examples (Fig. 2) for *nakhlebnitsa* (*scrounge – нахлебница*), but the cases recorded in the Russian National Corpus are in full accordance with the meaning that needs to be expressed in the translation, for instance: *A feeling of unforgiven guilt forced the girl to bypass the busy bumblebee on the flower: It was at home, at work, while she was a stranger, coming from the burnt Sapegin, a scrounge, cherished by the grace of kind people* (Чувство непрощенной вины заставило девушку обойти деловитого шмеля на цветке: он был свой тут, и за работой, а она - пришедшая, из сгоревшего Сапегина, **нахлебница**, пригретая по милости добрых людей) (Russian National Corpus).

Figure 1. Frequency curve of the phrase *kept mistress – содержанка* (per million, Russian National Corpus)

Figure 2. Frequency curve of the word *scrounge – нахлебница* (per million, Russian National Corpus)

Regarding the lexical item *toadeater* (Fig. 3), it can also be argued that it is one of the most accurate equivalents that can be used when translating Turkish *besleme*, but this word has a pragmatic message indicating social stratification, social position; the semantics of this word is narrower than the semantics of the word *scrounge*. The difference between them was that the noble toadeater kept company with only the noble ones, with merchants and petty bourgeoisies.

Figure 3. Frequency curve of the word *toadeater* – приживалка (per million, Russian National Corpus)

Based on the above material, it is clear that these translation solutions produce cognitive dissonance among the text recipients- the target audience of “TV Series.” Therefore, a qualified editor, at a minimum, is required to take into account the pragmatic change that has arisen as a result of the imperfection of the database that serves as the basis for the translation program and to eliminate the dissonance between the character and his/her verbal description provided by other characters.

A typical problem is the discrepancy between a word’s semantic and pragmatic components in the source and target languages. Let us consider this problem using the word *messing about with* as the example, which is dissonant with the surrounding context in terms of pragmatics (constantly, in all 89 cases recorded by us) and often semantics (in 44 cases out of 89):

*Being a family requires being open with each other and being honest. Being a family requires protecting and keeping each other safe. Being a family requires not to offend and respect. We are a family. But only in words. Unfortunately, it is so. It turns out that our family is out of value. The value I’ve been trying to create, the value I’ve been **messing about with** to leave behind after I pass away...*

*Быть семьей требует быть открытыми друг перед другом и честности. Быть семьей требует защищать и оберегать друг друга. Быть семьей требует не обижать и уважать. Мы семья. Но только на словах. К сожалению, это так. Оказывается, в нашей семье нет никакой ценности. Ценность, которую я старался построить, с которой **ВОЗНЕСЯ**, чтобы оставить после того, как я уйду на тот свет...*

*Aile olmak bir birine açık olmayı, dürüstlüğü gerektirir. Aile olmak bir birini korumayı kollamayı gerektirir. Aile olmak incitmemeyi saygı duymayı gerektirir. Biz bir aileyiz. Ama sadece sözde. Benim inşa etmeye çalıştım göçüp gittikten sonra arkamda bırakmayı **uğraştım** hiç bir diğer ailemizde yokmuş.*

First, the dictionary definition of the verb *mess about with* reflecting the meaning fixed in the usage, is as follows: 1. Noisy, restless, fussy move, gambol Children are *messing about* on the floor. 2. *mess about with* children. Someone is *messing about* in the corner. 3. *with something* *Messing about with* painstaking work (colloquial). *mess about with* luggage. *mess about with* the child. || *with and for something* hardly work, slowly (colloquial). The secretary spent a whole month *fiddling with* the report [TSU].

In addition to the apparent semantic change and breach of compatibility (*mess about with the value*), Russian meaning *hardly, slowly working on something* refers to the colloquial register (according to Ushakov’s dictionary – TSU), which is dissonant with the solemn and

gloomy tone of Hikmet's speech above. Besides, this word is used without any object while the context requires clarification of both pragmatics and the semantics of the verb, which is not required in the source language because *uğraşmak* – *to do, to mess about with* – does not always require an object, and this cannot but attract the attention of the translator, especially if it is a native speaker of the receptor language, but, of course, remains unattended when using artificial intelligence and other auxiliary tools of the modern translator which causes a pragmatic change and also prevents the understanding of the speaker's intentions:

*I'm OK, my dear, my life is fine. What could it be? **We're messing about***
*Я в порядке, жизнь моя, в порядке. Что может быть? **ВОЗИМСЯ***
*İyiyim, hayatım iyi ne olsun. **Uğraşıyoruz;***
*You **forced me messing about.** You'd better not to pull something off (about Zeynep's escape)*
*Ты **заставила** меня **ВОЗИТЬСЯ**, только попробуй что-то проверить*
*... yeter **uğraştırdığın.** Hele bi daba numara yapmaya kalk.*
*I myself didn't understand what was happening, what we **are messing about with, Suna?***
*(Я сама не поняла, что происходит, с чем мы **ВОЗИМСЯ**, Суна?)*
*...ben ne olduğumuzu, neyle **uğradığımızı** anladım mi acaba Suna?*

This is the case when flexibility is needed, which is inherent in the thinking of a professional translator since he/she will choose either *What are we doing*, or will translate it based on the context by making the subject of the action (*We*) as a passive participant and contemplator or transforming it to an object (such a transformation requires some time and considering the context): *What's happening to us? What happened to us?*

Inconsistency of connotations or emotive potential of words (presence of this factor in the source language/absence in the target language, etc.). In total, we identified 93 examples of this kind. Due to the limited space of this paper, we will focus on the most typical cases, including 101 examples. Thus, when watching Turkish TV Series, attention is drawn to the very unusual contextualization of a word, which in Russian is practically not endowed with any connotative meaning; also, it has no emotive potential and expresses relatively weak negative rational or even neutral characteristic, namely – the word *ill-mannered* (*man/woman*) (we identified 92 cases of its use in our material; however, it should be noted that in other Turkish “TV Series” it has a high frequency and, as a rule, sounds very expressive, accompanied by an angry, almost stigmatizing intonation):

*Do not be **ill-mannered**... yesterday you came from the village, and today you're giving me some instructions.*
*Не будь **невоспитанной**... вчера приехала из деревни, а сегодня раздаешь мне наставления какие-то*
***terbiyesizleşme** ... diin köyden geldin bugün bana akıl mı veriyorsun?*
*Keep an eye on your wife, dad! – You are an **Ill-mannered girl!***
*Ты за своей женой приглядывай, папа! – **Невоспитанная!***
*Karma sahib çık baba! - **Terbiyesiz!***

Note that in the second case, professional translation (duplication) uses an emotively close equivalent – an *insolent/impudent woman*); *Seiran, what the bad manners, what the contempt?! Сеіран, что за невоспитанность, что за неуважение?! Seyran bu ne terbiyesizlik, bu ne saygısızlık!* (“Golden Boy”) (neutral, almost unemotional reaction of the head of the family to a situation that is practically unacceptable in a traditional family: a young wife brings her husband into the room with a stick). For a native Russian speaker, this is just a lack of proper upbringing, i.e. ignorance of the rules

of conduct, perhaps rudeness, but not a violation of moral principles: Ill-mannered man, ill-mannered woman, mannerless; ill-bred man, ill-bred woman, badly behaved. A person, who does not have any proper upbringing (TSU). It should be pointed out that in Turkic cultures, upbringing, especially for a girl, is a very sensitive matter, and the word *terbiyesiz*, for example, in the Kazakh language, means that a girl who was raised by a whole clan was unable to perceive external rules of behavior, namely moral principles. An analogue might instead be a shameless man/woman or an unscrupulous man/unscrupulous woman. Still, such an equivalent can only be chosen by a person who has flexible thinking and considers the peculiarities of the perception of words in a particular culture, but not artificial intelligence.

According to Newmark (1988), it is necessary to transform the grammar of the source language by finding exact equivalents in the target language. Also, it is necessary to translate lexical words in a way that is appropriate directly in the context of the particular sentence (Newmark, 1988). Our material also widely represents problems related to translating idioms and their pragmatic coloring. As Baker (1992) stated it:

The source-language word may express a totally unknown concept in the target culture. The concept in question may be abstract or concrete; it may relate to a religious belief, a social custom, or even a type of food. Such concepts are often referred to as 'culture-specific' (Baker, 1992, p. 21)

The Turkish language contains many gratitude phrases and, in general, phrases used to demonstrate politeness (for example, in various situations where a native Russian speaker will say Thank you, the Turkish can use several analogues). We have focused on one gratitude set expression only; perhaps, it does not have an exact equivalent in Russian and which is very frequent in the material considered (there are 204 cases of *ellerine sağlık*, which is literary translated as *health to your hands* as a breach of the target language rules because in Russian they wish health to a person but not parts of the body). Such a phrase in the source language is used as an expression of gratitude for something done well, and this is mainly a tangible action done with hands, having a material result (for example, a well-prepared cup of coffee served, a deliciously prepared lunch, etc.). Besides, in several cases, we note the translation using such a cliché that is entirely inappropriate for the context; for instance, in such soap opera as *The Golden Boy*: in a fit of anger, one of the characters of the series, a timid and downtrodden woman, knocks down the lock on the closet and then tells to her daughter. Daughter's reaction:

*Did you break the lock with pots and pans? **Health to your hands!***
*Ты что, кастрюлями и сковородками ломала замок? **Здоровья твоим рукам!!***
*Tencere ile tava ile dolabı vurup parçaladın mı yani? **Aferin sana! Eline sağlık!***

The expression, *Thank you*, depends on the situation and context, and a variety of meanings based on the necessary contextual environment can be conveyed only using professional translation, which requires time. It is an amateur translation, so there is a lack of text editing in the target language and no relevant idioms in the target language. On the other hand, that indicates the lack of adaptation, which is considered a core value in professional translation; so, professional translation can be optimized by applying a translation program but in no way replaced by its use.

5. Conclusion

Translation accuracy is critical in passing the message across, as pragmatically faulty language constructions tend to make dialogues rather challenging to comprehend while creating or

fostering misconceptions about the target culture (Arikan, 2007, p. 12). Even when (amateur) translators use automatic translation at work, analyses of the TV series indicate that automatic translation can only optimize human translation but cannot replace it in any way, even in translating a relatively simple text, as can be found in TV series.

First, contextualization fundamentally differs from the printed text in audio-visual translation, as audio-visual material represents non-verbalized information (facial expressions, gestures, video sequences, etc.), which is particularly important. Diaz-Cintas's (2008) paper describes the reasons behind such difficulties. The difficulty with audio-visual translation includes but is not limited to the fact that studies in this field have been focused for many years on printed text. The researcher focuses that we are dealing not so much with the translation itself but with the text adaptation, which, in turn, complicates discussions about the essence of audio-visual translation. However, the situation rapidly changes as translation becomes more flexible and adapts to new realities (Diaz-Cintas, 2008).

Besides, a low-quality translation can play the opposite role, i.e. contribute to the development of negative processes such as the reduction of speech culture of the target language native speakers. It is also necessary to consider Il'yushkina's (2015) statement concerning the quality of translation. Thus, the results of translation (translation quality) are determined by the degree of semantic similarity of the target text to the source text, the genre and stylistic similarity between the source and the target text, and pragmatics influencing the choice of equivalent, and, generally, the way to render the particular phenomenon (Shintemirova et al., 2024). All these aspects of translation are directly normative and determine the translators' strategies and criteria for evaluating their work.

There is evident importance of a detailed representation of concepts, singling out as many semantic components as possible and entering them into the database to optimize the translation process to improve the quality of the translation program, but not to replace a human translator with a translation program. Currently, computer program development can only be a human tool or assistant where it is necessary to save translators' time, minimize mechanical work, and create conditions for creative translation, which is only a peculiar feature of flexible human intellect.

In addition, a detailed representation of concepts is essential, singling out as many semantic components as possible and entering them into the database to optimize the translation process and improve the translation program's quality, but not to replace a human translator with a translation program. Currently, computer program development can only be a human tool, where it is necessary to save translators' time, minimize mechanical work, and create conditions for creative translation, which is only a peculiar feature of flexible human intellect.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 20/05/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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